

Transformer vs CNN: A Comparative Study of Wheat Spike Detection Under Field Conditions

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ABSTRACT:

Wheat spike detection plays an important role in phenotyping, as it provides an approach for direct yield estimation and serves as an indicator of yield potential. Traditional method of phenotyping involved manual counting of wheat heads which is a time-consuming, and error-prone process. However, the advent of Deep Learning (DL) techniques has revolutionized this process by allowing automated detection and counting of wheat heads using high-resolution imagery, hence facilitating large-scale, High Throughput Phenotyping (HTP) of wheat. Despite technological advancements, issues related to environmental variability, differences among cultivars, and overlapping heads continue to make automated detection task difficult and error-prone. To address these issues, researchers have focused on enhancing the robustness of DL models and increasing the diversity of wheat head datasets to improve detection accuracy and reliability of this approach. In this study, we have compared the performance of three state-of-the-art DL models, YOLOv10x, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO, for wheat head detection. To ensure diversity of the dataset, we have integrated two datasets, the Global Wheat Head Detection (GWHD) 2021 and the SPIKE dataset representing various wheat genotypes. This study aims to advance wheat head detection methods and offer a comparative evaluation of these three DL models.

Keywords: Weat spike, detection, wheat head, High-throughput, Phenotyping, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network, Transformer, CNN, Object detection.

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INTRODUCTION

Wheat is a staple food source for most of the global population and plays a critical role in global food security [1]. Maximization of wheat production is crucial in the face of climate change and rapid population growth. Hence, breeding efforts all around the world must be expedited with advancements in genotyping and phenotyping efforts. Despite the improvement in wheat genotyping in recent years due to technologies such as SNP arrays and next-generation sequencing (NGS), phenotyping techniques have not kept pace [2]. Phenotyping efforts also need to be improved using HTP approaches leveraging cutting-edge sensors and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies for advancements in wheat breeding efforts.

In wheat breeding, spike count and properties like kernel size or weight are direct indicators of yield, helping breeders in selecting promising cultivars [3-5]. Automation in phenotyping for counting or detection of wheat heads enables breeders to monitor yield-related traits without depending upon labor-intensive manual counting [6]. Advanced imaging sensors and deep learning (DL) technologies facilitate automated wheat head detection with high speed and reliability.

Machine Learning (ML) and DL models using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been widely adopted in several Computer Vision related tasks. This also includes precision agriculture, in applications such as in weed and crop monitoring [7]. Beyond CNN-based DL models, transformer-based architectures, including large language models (LLMs) and computer vision models, are being widely adopted across multiple domains [8]. DL models can process high-resolution imagery of wheat canopy and operate efficiently with large volumes of data, supporting high-throughput phenotyping (HTP). When trained on diverse datasets covering various treatment systems and environments, robustness and accuracy of DL models can be improved.

However, using AI for wheat head detection is challenging due to variability in field conditions and canopy properties such as color, illumination, spike overlap, and canopy cover introducing artifacts in the images or wheat dataset. Hence, the genotypic and phenotypic diversity of wheat or wheat heads leads to inaccuracies in wheat detection models trained on limited datasets. To ensure optimal model performance, the diversity of training data is as important as DL model complexity for accurate detection of wheat heads [10].

Several attempts have been made by scientists globally to improve the accuracy of wheat head detection by adopting state-of-the-art detection models and introducing diverse datasets [11-13]. In our study, we evaluate the performance of three cutting-edge DL models, RetinaNet, MM-Grounding DINO, and YOLOv11, for high-throughput wheat spike detection. By combining the Global Wheat Head Detection (GWHD) 2021 dataset [11] and the SPIKE dataset [6], we have created a diverse dataset representing a wide range of genotypes and environmental conditions. The aim of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of these state-of-the-art DL models for wheat spike detection in varied conditions and contribute to the ongoing evolution of automated wheat head detection processes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The workflow for comparative analysis of wheat spike detection models started with the dataset preparation and compilation. In this study, we have combined two popular wheat spike datasets, GWHD_2021 and SPIKE dataset, which contain high-resolution images of wheat spikes captured from diverse environmental conditions and wheat varieties. This step was followed by data pre-processing step where dataset was prepared for model training. Model evaluation was also performed using suitable evaluation metrics for the comparison of different detection models.

Figure 1. System Block Diagram for the Comparison of Wheat Spike Detection Models

Dataset Description

In this study, we utilized two datasets: the GWHD_2021 dataset [11] and the SPIKE dataset [6]. Both of these datasets have several key differences and similarities in terms of several key aspects, including camera angles, illumination conditions, and other environmental factors, making the final combined dataset robust and diverse.

Figure 2. Diverse Images of Wheat Heads Captured at Different Growth Stages

The Global Wheat Head Detection Dataset was initially compiled by collaborators from all over the world and is one of the most comprehensive dataset available for wheat head detection. Initially published on 2020, it consisted of 4700 high-resolution RGB images and 190000 labelled wheat heads collected from several countries around the world. Afterwards, an updated version was released on 2021 called the GWHD_2021 dataset, with improvements and refinements to the GWHD_2020 dataset. The improvements to the initial datasets involved eliminating low quality wheat spike images, relabeling for consistency, and adding images from a much wider range of developmental stages from the original sites. The updated version of the GWHD_2021 consisted of 6500 high resolution imagery consisting of 275,187 unique wheat spikes with corresponding bounding boxes. GWHD_2021 dataset is split into 3600 images for training, 1400 for testing and

1400 for model validation. Alternatively, the SPIKE dataset consisted of over 300 images of ten different wheat varieties captured at three distinct growth stages, and hence offering a detailed perspective on spike development. Despite being a smaller dataset, SPIKE dataset provided more variability or diversity to the final dataset.

Table 1. Dataset Description

Category	Images Count	Head Count
Training Data	5254	252867
Validation Data	1476	44347
Total	6730	297214

In this study, the majority of training data was taken from the GWHD_2021 dataset, using both its training and test images. To enhance the diversity and robustness of the training data, we supplemented it with selected positive examples from the SPIKE dataset—those containing clearly labeled wheat spikes. In total, our training dataset consisted of 1,400 training and 1,400 test images from GWHD_2021, along with 315 images from the SPIKE dataset. For validation, we used 1,400 images from the validation split of the GWHD_2021 dataset.

Dataset Pre-Processing

The GWHD_2021 dataset originally had annotations in the widely adopted COCO format, commonly used in object detection tasks. In contrast, the SPIKE dataset had its annotations in a separate TSV files that contained bounding box coordinates and class labels for each image. Since our selected models each require different annotation format, YOLOv10 requires the dataset to be in YOLO format, MM-Grounding DINO works with COCO format, and RetinaNet accepts either COCO or a structured CSV format. Hence, the dataset was pre-processed according to the model requirements.

To prepare the datasets for training and evaluation, we reformatted the annotations from both GWHD_2021 and SPIKE to align with the specific input requirements of each model. This involved restructuring the annotation files to ensure compatibility with each model's format expectations for bounding boxes and class labels. These conversions were essential to ensure smooth model integration and accurate training outcomes.

- **YOLOv10 Format:** For each image, a corresponding .txt file was created. Each line in the file represents one bounding box, with values for the class ID, normalized center coordinates (center_x, center_y), and normalized width and height relative to the image dimensions. This lightweight format is designed for efficient training with YOLO models.
- **RetinaNet Format:** Annotations were compiled into a CSV file, with each row detailing a bounding box for a specific image. Each row contains the image filename, the bounding box coordinates (xmin, ymin, xmax, ymax), and a class label—set as "wheat" for all entries. This structured format is ideal for RetinaNet's tabular annotation processing.
- **MM-Grounding DINO Format (COCO):** A COCO-style JSON file was created containing image metadata, bounding boxes, and category information. This format is comprehensive and supports complex detection tasks, making it suitable for Grounding DINO and similar models that rely on rich annotation data.

Experimentation

The three cutting-edge models, YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO, were trained using a combined set of training data pre-processed according to the required input format for the models. This dataset included images from both the training and testing splits of the GWHD_2021 dataset, complemented by positive examples from the SPIKE dataset. The models were trained using NVIDIA P100 GPU on the Kaggle. Pytorch was used as primary deep learning framework for the experimentation in this study.

The YOLOv10x model was trained for a total of 45 epochs with a batch size of 8. Input images were standardized to 800 × 800 pixels to ensure consistent dimensions across the dataset. The training

process employed an automatic optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.01, which was adjusted according to a predefined learning rate schedule. A 3-epoch warmup phase was included, starting with an initial learning rate of 0.1 and a warmup momentum of 0.8. Additional training parameters included a momentum value of 0.937 and a weight decay of 0.0005. To enhance computational efficiency, Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) was enabled. Data augmentation techniques such as horizontal flipping (with a probability of 0.5), random scaling, and mosaic augmentation were applied during the initial 10 epochs, with auto-augmentation configured to use randaugment to further improve data diversity. The training process incorporated overlap mask regularization with a mask ratio of 4, while dropout was not used.

For RetinaNet model training, ResNet-152 backbone within the RetinaNet model was employed. The training process began by initializing the backbone with pre-trained weights from a ResNet-101 checkpoint, which had been trained on ImageNet. This allowed us to leverage the strong feature extraction capabilities of ResNet, particularly for identifying intricate features in the wheat heads. The ResNet backbone was fine-tuned to adapt to our wheat detection task, while the classification and regression heads of the RetinaNet model were trained from scratch. This hybrid approach was necessary to transfer generalized features learned from ImageNet while modifying the model for the detection of wheat heads. To improve the model's generalization ability, we applied various data augmentations, including normalization, resizing, and horizontal flipping. These augmentations were critical in simulating real-world variations in wheat head appearances. We set a confidence threshold of 0.3 to filter out low-confidence detections and used an Intersection-over-Union (IoU) threshold of 0.5 to determine true positives based on the overlap between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes. To ensure efficiency, we capped the maximum number of detections per image at 100. For optimization, the Adam optimizer was employed with a learning rate of $1e-5$, and a learning rate scheduler was used to reduce the learning rate when validation loss plateaued. We trained the model for 100 epochs, incorporating gradient clipping with a threshold of 5 to prevent overfitting and manage exploding gradients. The total loss function minimized was a combination of classification loss (focal loss) and regression loss (smooth L1) for bounding box predictions.

We utilized the MM-Grounding DINO framework with the `grounding_dino_swin-t_pretrain_obj365` model for wheat head detection. The dataset used in training this model were images with annotations following the COCO format. To facilitate detection of wheat heads, we defined a single class labeled as "wheat". The training dataset was augmented using a combination of random flips and random choice resize operations across a range of scales, with additional cropping to account for the high aspect ratio of the images. For data loading, we employed a custom pipeline that processed images and annotations in batches, utilizing a sampler to ensure a balanced distribution of image aspect ratios. The model was optimized using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and weight decay of 0.0001. A gradient clipping strategy with a maximum norm of 0.1 was applied to stabilize training. Training was conducted over 8 epochs. We initialized our model from pre-trained weights provided by the MMDetection team.

Validation Metrics

In this study, we utilized Intersection over Union (IoU), Average Precision (AP), and Recall as evaluation or validation metrics to evaluate the performance of YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding DINO models. IoU measures the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth box, which is essential for determining whether a detection is considered a true positive. IoU is calculated as:

$$\text{IoU} = \text{Area of Overlap} / \text{Area of Union} \quad (1)$$

where the Area of Overlap is the intersection area between the predicted and ground truth boxes, and the Area of Union is their combined area. A detection is considered a true positive if the IoU exceeds a predefined threshold, i.e. 0.5 in our case.

Precision represents the ratio of True Positive (TP) detections to the total number of positive detections and is critical for assessing how accurately each model identified wheat heads without generating False Positives (FP). Mathematically, precision is defined as:

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / \max(\text{TP} + \text{FP}, \epsilon) \quad (2)$$

where TP represents the number of correctly identified wheat heads, and FP refers to instances where the model incorrectly predicted the presence of wheat heads. The small constant ϵ is introduced to prevent division by zero in the case where there are no positive predictions. Precision was particularly important for reducing false positives, which could lead to over-estimations in crop yield or incorrect decisions in downstream agricultural processes.

Recall, the ratio of true positive detections to the total number of actual instances, provided insights into the models' sensitivity and their capacity to detect most wheat heads, even in challenging conditions. High recall ensured that the models captured most relevant wheat heads, but it needed to be balanced with precision to avoid an excessive number of false positives. Mathematically, recall is defined as:

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / \text{TP} + \text{FN} \quad (3)$$

We also used Average Precision (AP) as a metric for evaluating model performance, as it provides a comprehensive measure of performance by considering both precision and recall across various thresholds. AP is computed by integrating the precision-recall curve, which plots precision versus recall at different threshold levels. It can also be defined as the area under the precision-recall curve.

In this paper, Average Precision (AP) is used as the primary metric for evaluating performance. Since the analysis is focused on a single class, the mean Average Precision (mAP) and AP are equivalent in this context.

RESULTS

The evaluation results for the wheat head detection task are summarized in table below, presenting the performance of three models YOLOv10, RetinaNet, and MM-Grounding-DINO.

Table 2. Performance Comparison of Models Used for Wheat Head Detection

Model	AP@50	Precision	Recall
RetinaNet	0.841	0.839	0.860
YOLOv10	0.912	0.894	0.844
MM-Grounding-DINO	0.922	0.888	0.924

Among all the models compared in this study, MM-Grounding DINO achieved the highest average precision (AP@50) score of 0.922, outperforming the other two models in the detection of wheat spikes. The precision for this model was 0.888 and recall was 0.924, demonstrating the model's ability effectively identify true positives with minimal false positive detection, outperforming other models in both detection accuracy and consistency.

The performance of YOLOv10 model for spike detection was also reasonably good with an AP@50 of 0.912. The precision score of 0.894 for YOLOV10 was highest among the models, showing its strength in minimizing false positives. Alternatively, the recall for this model was slightly lower at 0.844. RetinaNet had the lowest overall performance, with an AP@50 of 0.841, precision of 0.839, and recall of 0.860. While its results were balanced, it lagged behind in terms of overall detection effectiveness.

Overall, MM-Grounding DINO emerged as the best-performing model and had the best balance between precision and recall. YOLOv10 showed its value in spike detection with a high precision value, while RetinaNet, despite providing balanced results, was less accurate than the other two.

The performance of models in wheat spike detection can be seen in figure 3. The figure shows the performance of models under different environmental conditions and wheat genotypes. MM-Grounding DINO's predictions are significantly better, even in images with overlapping wheat spikes, showing its robustness. YOLOv10 also performed well, though it tended to miss smaller or partially hidden heads, consistent with its lower recall. RetinaNet's bounding boxes appeared less precise, particularly when detecting small or overlapping wheat heads.

Figure 3. Wheat Head Detection Results from Different Models (a) MM-Grounding DINO, (b) YOLOV10, and (c) RetinaNet, Showing Bounding Box Predictions for Wheat Heads

DISCUSSION

In this study, MM-Grounding DINO demonstrated superior performance over YOLOv10 and RetinaNet, particularly in scenarios involving overlapping wheat heads and complex backgrounds. This suggests that transformer-based models may offer greater efficiency in wheat head detection compared to traditional CNN-based models, especially under challenging field conditions. The improved performance of the transformer-based approach can be credited to its architecture, which excels at capturing long-range dependencies and contextual cues, making it more resilient where CNNs often face limitations.

Nonetheless, techniques such as model regularization, ensembling, and data augmentation have shown promise in enhancing the precision of CNN-based models [6,10]. These strategies can strengthen the generalization and robustness of CNN models across diverse conditions. Future work may focus on leveraging the complementary strengths of both CNN and transformer-based architectures to further enhance the accuracy and reliability of wheat head detection.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that transformer-based models, particularly MM-Grounding DINO, outperformed traditional CNN-based models like YOLOv10 and RetinaNet in detecting wheat heads under difficult conditions, such as overlapping spikes and complex field backgrounds. MM-Grounding DINO's superior performance is likely attributed to its capacity to model intricate spatial and contextual relationships, making it more effective in diverse and variable field environments. While CNN-based models tend to struggle in such scenarios, their performance can be enhanced through techniques like regularization, data augmentation, and model ensembling. For more robust and fair comparisons in future studies, advanced training and validation strategies—such as early stopping, augmentation, and ensemble learning—should be explored to further improve model accuracy and reliability.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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